

GREEN SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES USING LEAF EXTRACT FROM *CITRUS LIMON* (L.) OSBECK AND ITS ANTIBACTERIAL, ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITIES

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Article Received on 21 April 2026,
Article Revised on 12 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20442634>

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How To Cite This Article: Sunitha V. Hegde, Girisha S. T., Dilip Kumar R., Rajeshwari H. Patil, Hemanth K.C., Narasimhamurthy K.*. (2026). Green Synthesis and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles Using Leaf Extract from Citrus Limon (L.) Osbeck and its Antibacterial, Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Activities. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 582–611.

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ABSTRACT

The present research comprise of green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) by *Citrus limon* leaf extracts and to assess the antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. The synthesized AgNPs were characterized using UV–Vis spectroscopy, FTIR, SEM and XRD, which collectively confirmed the successful formation of stable and crystalline nanoparticles with defined particle sizes. UV–Vis analysis showed a surface plasmon resonance (SPR) peak centered at 405 nm, indicating the presence of AgNPs. The FTIR spectrum revealed distinct absorption bands at 2072.96 cm^{-1} , 642.45 cm^{-1} , and 620.55 cm^{-1} , suggesting the involvement of functional groups in stabilization. SEM analysis demonstrated that the nanoparticles had an irregular morphology, with a broad size distribution and noticeable aggregation. Particle size measurements in selected areas ranged from 79.4 to 222 nm. Furthermore, XRD analysis exhibited five prominent diffraction peaks at 38.00° , 44.04° , 45.63° , 64.29° , and 77.28° ,

which correspond to the (111), (200), (210), (220), and (311) planes of face-centered cubic silver, confirming their crystalline structure. Bioactivity assays revealed that - AgNPs from *Citrus limon* exhibited significant antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities.

Zone of inhibition increases with concentrations 25- 200µg/ml. The highest zone of inhibition 16 mm for *B. subtilis* and 15 mm for *E. mori* was observed at 200µg/ml. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) assay of *C. limon*-AgNPs demonstrated a dose-dependent antimicrobial effect, the lowest concentration of 5 µg/ml was inhibition of 9.09%. The antioxidant activity of *C. limon*-derived AgNPs was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay, and concentration-dependent increase in radical scavenging activity, with inhibition ranging from 9.2% at 25 µg/ml to 32.3% at 200 µg/ml. The anti-inflammatory activity of *C. limon* derived AgNPs increased in a concentration dependent manner with inhibition ranging from 8.45% at 25 µg/ml to 20.41% at 200 µg/ml. Based on our studies, further identification of the major compounds of leaf extracts is acceptable.

KEYWORDS: *Citrus limon*, silver nanoparticles, antibacterial, antioxidant minimum inhibitory concentration, anti-inflammatory.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing failure of chemotherapeutics and development of bacterial resistance to currently available antibiotics has imposed the search for novel and effective antimicrobial compounds from natural resources. Plant-derived medicines have gained immense importance in recent years because of their potential efficacy with negligible side effects (Riaz *et al.*, 2023). Plants are a rich source of valuable secondary metabolites such as tannins, terpenes, terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, coumarins, polysaccharides, glycosides, gum and phenols that are used by plants as defense mechanisms against invasion by many microorganisms, insects, and herbivores (El-Saadony *et al.*, 2025; Adedayo *et al.*, 2025). Several studies have reported that plants synthesize a wide range of bioactive substances contribute to their pharmacological potential and ecological defense mechanisms (Kamaraj *et al.*, 2012; Chaachouay and Zidane 2024). Medicinal plants have been an important source of therapeutic agents for centuries. India possesses a long-standing tradition of knowledge related to plant-based medicines, used for both prevention and treatment of diseases since ancient times, as documented in systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha, Homeopathy, and other traditional practices. Approximately 88% of the global population uses plant-based drugs or medicines as their first line of defense for maintaining health and combating many diseases. Plant-derived medicines are often perceived as more acceptable to the human body compared to modern synthetic drugs (Anbukkarasi *et al.*, 2016; Biswas *et al.*, 2015; Chaachouay *et al.*, 2021).

Within the *Rutaceae* family, coumarins are especially abundant, with compounds such as marmelosin and luvangetin being well documented. These phytochemicals are associated with diverse therapeutic activities, including antihelminthic, antiulcer, antibacterial, and antispasmodic effects, thereby validating their importance in traditional medicine as well as modern phytopharmacology (Greger, 2017; Thakur *et al.*, 2025). The most recent phylogenetic analysis of the *Rutaceae* includes 135 genera, representing approximately 87.7% of the currently recognized diversity within the family (Appelhans *et al.*, 2021). Members of this family are well known for producing physiologically active essential oils, which are widely distributed across species such as *Citrus limon* (lemon). *Citrus limon* is an economically important citrus species, with the genus citrus comprising approximately 70 species (Bora *et al.*, 2020; Rahman, 2022; Bussmann *et al.*, 2025). Globally, lemon ranks as the third most widely cultivated citrus crop, following orange and mandarin, highlighting its significant agricultural and commercial value with pharmacological properties. It is one of the world's most planted fruit crops, with an annual worldwide production of 124.3 million tons (Klimek-Szczykutowicz *et al.*, 2020). Because of their high levels of bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, polyphenols and vitamins (Saini *et al.*, 2022; Vetere *et al.*, 2025). The leaves of *C. limon* contain a diverse range of bioactive compounds, particularly secondary metabolites, that contribute to their medicinal value and aromatic profile have been valued in traditional medicine and culinary applications. Additionally, several biological compounds extracted from citrus leaves display strong insecticidal and repellent activity and their potential role as fumigants (Dev Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2016; Paw *et al.*, 2020; Vetere *et al.*, 2025).

The *C. limon* leaves are elliptical to lanceolate, green and emit a distinct citrus fragrance due to their rich essential oil content. Traditionally *C. limon* leaves have been used as herbal infusions for relieving anxiety, digestive discomfort, and fever, as well as for flavoring soups, teas and meats (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008). Several studies have shown that *Citrus limon* fruit cultivars could be employed to improve human health as antimicrobial and anti-oxidative (Otang *et al.*, 2016; Ehiobu *et al.*, 2021; Posadino *et al.*, 2025) anti-inflammatory (Basli *et al.*, 2016) and anti-tumor products (Dosoky and Setzer, 2018). The *C. limon* have very rich in bioactive substances, such as citric acid, phenolic compounds flavonoids, and carotenoids and ascorbic acid (Saini *et al.*, 2022; Anna Maria *et al.*, 2025).

Nanotechnology can be defined as research for synthesis, manipulation and design, and the

structure of particles with element size about 1- 100 nm. Metal mediated nanoparticles have a high precise surface area and a high fraction of surface atoms. Because of the distinctive physicochemical features of nanoparticles include catalytic activity, optical and electronic properties, antibacterial potential and magnetic properties (Hidayat *et al.*, 2023; Abbas *et al.*, 2024). The secondary metabolites present in plant extracts such as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, etc., will reduce the metallic compounds into its nano compounds. For stabilization the active compounds will act as capping agents and enhance the activity of both nanoparticle and act as therapeutic compounds. Silver nanoparticles are widely recognized as non-toxic and safe inorganic antibacterial agents, and their antimicrobial properties have been utilized for centuries (Dhaka *et al.*, 2023). They exhibit strong activity against a broad range of microorganisms responsible for various diseases (Abdullah *et al.*, 2024). Among the different types of nanomaterials like copper, silver zinc, titanium, magnesium, gold and alginate, silver-based nanoparticles demonstrated as the most active since it has virtuous antimicrobial effectiveness against wide range of microorganisms including eukaryotic (Jiang *et al.*, 2024). Hence AgNPs has been incorporated medical items like clothing, catheters, dressings, surgical and dental products (Pandiyan *et al.*, 2023). Silver nanoparticles are being used as a drug delivery system and an effective drug for cancer treatment (Abbas *et al.*, 2024). They have a higher surface and greater capacity when compared to bulk form, specific catalytic, electrical and optical features pave the way for these nanoparticles to be applied in diagnosis, imaging, detection and targeted drug delivery (Gupta *et al.*, 2024). The other features include enhanced pharmacokinetics, robust therapeutic effect, less toxicity and supports biocompatibility (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Different techniques are used to determine the size of the nanoparticles like TEM, SEM, XRD, dynamic light scattering and AFM (Fatima *et al.*, 2024; Konappa *et al.*, 2021). Nanoparticles can be synthesized mainly by three methods: physical, chemical and biological (Chowdavarapu *et al.*, 2025). Green synthesis of nanoparticles is widely preferred due to its multiple advantages, low cost involved, reduced risk of adverse effects, more economical, safe products, suitable for pharmaceutical industries and other applications, while also contributing to the protection of human health (Amani *et al.*, 2024).

Plant derived extracts serve a dual purpose, functioning both as reducing agents and stabilizing agents, making the process simple and effective (Villagrán *et al.*, 2024; Hanna *et al.*, 2025). The bio-reduction mechanism is driven by diverse biomolecules naturally present in plants such as enzymes, proteins, amino acids, vitamins, polysaccharides and citrates which enable

the formation of stable nanoparticles (Hanna *et al.*, 2025). Given their critical role, plants are considered an invaluable component in bio-based strategies for synthesizing environmentally friendly and chemically complex metal nanoparticles (Cardoso *et al.*, 2025). The concept of using plant-based biosynthesis to produce metallic nanoparticles has rapidly gained attention. This eco-friendly approach, which relies on inactive plant tissues, plant extracts or even live plants, offers an innovative and sustainable alternative to conventional chemical and physical synthesis methods. Employing plant sources for nanoparticle synthesis is not only cost-efficient but also well-suited for large-scale production (Alsammarraie *et al.*, 2023; Cardoso *et al.*, 2025). Due to their environmentally friendly and biocompatible nature, biological synthesis nanoparticles have found widespread applications in both healthcare and environmental clean-up (Waris *et al.*, 2021, Augustine and Hasan 2020; Ayub *et al.*, 2025). The present study aimed to develop an eco-friendly approach for the synthesis of AgNPs using leaf extracts and evaluation of the synthesized AgNPs for their antibacterial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. The synthesized nanoparticles were systematically characterized through analytical techniques including UV–Vis spectroscopy, FTIR, XRD, and SEM to evaluate their structural, morphological, and functional attributes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and preparation of plant extract

Fresh leaves of *Citrus limon* was collected from village Nagenahalli, near magadi and Jnana bharathi campus, Bengaluru, Karnataka respectively (Figure 1). The plant material was authenticated by the Central Ayurveda Research Institute, functioning under the Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India, and affiliated with the Central Council for Research in Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS), Bengaluru (PIN: 560109).

Figure 1: *Citrus limon* leaves.

The disease free leaves were carefully harvested and initially cleaned by rinsing under running tap water (2–3 times), followed by distilled water to remove surface impurities (Dell'Annunziata *et al.*, 2024). The cleaned leaves were then oven dried at 60 °C for 24 h and

ground into a fine powder using an electric blender. Aqueous extraction was carried out by mixing 10 g of leaf powder with 100 mL of distilled water, followed by refluxing the mixture at 70 °C for 2 h under continuous stirring to enhance the solubilization of bioactive compounds. After extraction, the mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper to obtain a clear filtrate, which was collected in a clean beaker (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Preparation of *Citrus limon* leaf extract.

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

The aqueous leaf extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening following standard methods. The presence or absence of phytochemicals in the *C. limon* leaf extract were tested.

Test for phenols (Ferric chloride test): Two ml of 5% solution of FeCl_3 was added to 1 ml plant leaf extracts. A black color of the reaction mixture was developed which confirms the presence of phenol (Harborne, 1973).

Test for Alkaloids (Mayer's reagent test): Three ml of plant leaf extract was added to 3 ml of 1% HCl solution and it was heated for 20 min on a water bath. The resulting reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature and used for Mayer's test. To the cooled reaction mixture in a test tube, 1 ml of Mayer's reagent was added drop by drop. The formation of a greenish colored cream precipitate indicated for the presence of alkaloids.

Test for Flavonoids (Alkaline reagent test): Three ml of plant leaf extract were treated with 1 ml of 10% NaOH solution. The formation of an intense yellow color confirms the presence of flavonoids (Harborne, 1973).

Test for anthraquinones (Bontrager's test): To 0.2 ml of plant leaf extract, 5 ml of chloroform and 5 mL of ammonia solution was added. The presence of bright pink color in the aqueous layer indicated the presence of anthraquinones.

Test for terpenoids and steroids: (Salkowski test): Five ml of plant leaf extract solution was mixed in 2 ml of chloroform, and 3 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid was layered on it. The reddish brown coloration of the interface was formed to indicate the presence of terpenoids. Red color at the lower surface indicates the presence of steroid.

Test for tannins (a) Ferric chloride test: To 0.5 ml plant leaf extract solution, 1 ml distilled water and 2 drops of ferric chloride solution was added, formation of blue-black coloration was indicates the presence of tannins.

(b) Lead acetate test: Ten percent lead acetate solution was added to 0.5 ml of plant leaf extract solution and white precipitation confirms the presence of tannins.

Test for saponins (Frothing test): To 0.2 ml of the plant leaf extracts was mixed with 5 ml of distilled water and then heated to boil. The appearance of froth reveals the presence of saponin.

Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extract

Silver nanoparticles were synthesized using a 1:2 volume ratio of 1 mM of silver nitrate solution to plant extract (100 ml:200 ml), where the plant extract acted as both reducing and capping agent and silver nitrate served as the precursor. The reaction mixture was incubated at temperature of 40°C for 90 min in a closed incubator. The visual color change from pale yellow to dark brown indicated the formation of AgNPs. The synthesized colloidal AgNPs were subjected to high- speed centrifugation at 10,000–15,000 rpm for 10–20 min to sediment the nanoparticles. The supernatant, containing unreacted phytochemicals and soluble impurities, was carefully discarded, while the nanoparticle pellet was collected for further study (Gopinath *et al.*, 2013).

Characterization of synthesized silver nanoparticles

The synthesized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from *C. limon* leaf extract were characterized using UV–Vis spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) analysis, X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

UV- Vis Spectroscopy analysis of silver nanoparticles

The synthesis of AgNPs was initially confirmed by the visual color change of the reaction mixture from pale yellow to brown, which indicates the excitation of surface plasmon vibrations in AgNPs. The reduction of silver ions (Ag^+) to metallic AgNPs was further confirmed using UV–Visible spectroscopy. The absorption spectrum of the colloidal solutions was recorded from the range of 300–600 nm using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer, where a distinct peak corresponding to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band of AgNPs was observed (Ahmed *et al.*, 2016; Gopinath *et al.*, 2013).

Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to examine the functional groups responsible for the reduction and stabilization of the biosynthesized AgNPs. The spectrum was recorded from the range of $4000\text{--}450\text{cm}^{-1}$ using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum, two spectrophotometer with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Earlier to analysis, the AgNPs sample was dried and finely ground with potassium bromide (KBr) to form a pellet, which was then scanned for infrared absorption. The FTIR spectrum reveals the characteristic vibrational modes of biomolecules involved in capping and stabilization of nanoparticles, including hydroxyl, carboxyl, amine, and aromatic groups. Such functional groups from phytochemicals act as reducing and stabilizing agents, preventing agglomeration and enhancing nanoparticle stability (Shukla and Iravani, 2017).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

The surface morphology of the biosynthesized AgNPs was examined using a SEM (Hitachi S-3400N). For sample preparation, a thin layer of dried nanoparticle powder was mounted on a carbon-coated aluminum stub and sputter-coated with a thin conductive layer to enhance surface conductivity and reduce charging effects during imaging. The analysis was performed at an accelerating voltage of 10.0 kV with a working distance of 5.7 mm, and micrographs were obtained at a magnification of $6000\times$ under secondary electron (SE) mode (Al-Rajhi *et al.*, 2022).

X- Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis

The crystalline structure of the biosynthesized AgNPs was characterized using XRD analysis. The diffraction pattern was recorded on a Rigaku Smart Lab diffractometer equipped with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) operated at 40 kV and 30 mA. The scanning was carried out over a 2θ range of 20° – 80° with a step size of 0.02° and a scan speed of $2^\circ/\text{min}$. The obtained diffractogram was analyzed using PDXL software for phase identification, peak indexing, and crystallite size determination. The average crystallite size of the nanoparticles was calculated using the Debye–Scherrer equation, where D is crystallite size, λ is X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg's angle (Singh and Gupta, 2023).

Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of biosynthesized AgNPs, as well as aqueous leaf extracts of *Citrus limon*, was assessed using the agar well diffusion method. Mueller–Hinton agar plates were swabbed with pre-grown bacterial suspensions of Gram positive bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis* MTCC No 2414) and Gram negative bacteria (*Enterobacter mori*) in Nutrient broth (1×10^8 CFU/plate) and Wells (6 mm) were aseptically punched and each well was filled with 50 μl of different concentrations (25, 50, 75, 100, 150, and 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of synthesized AgNPs, with appropriate positive and negative controls. Chloramphenicol served as a positive control. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h, after incubation the antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibitions around the wells (Tang and Zheng, 2018; Konappa *et al.*, 2021).

Assay of minimum inhibitory concentration

The antibacterial activity of biosynthesized AgNPs was assessed using the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) assay by using broth microdilution method. Serial dilutions of biosynthesized AgNPs were prepared in sterile microtiter plates and inoculated with bacterial suspensions. The MIC was recorded as the lowest concentration of AgNPs that inhibited visible bacterial growth when compared with the control (Baker *et al.*, 2021).

Briefly, 50 μl of AgNPs suspensions prepared in Luria–Bertani (LB) broth was added to 96 well plates in decreasing concentrations (160, 80, 40, 20, 10, and 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Bacterial cultures were grown in LB broth and adjusted to a 0.5 McFarland standard (1×10^8 CFU/ml). The 50 μl of bacterial inoculum was added to each well containing AgNPs dilutions. Chloramphenicol served as positive control, while sterile deionized water was used as the

negative control. The plates were sealed and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. After incubation, 10 µl of Alamar Blue dye was added to each well and the plates were further incubated for 3 h in the dark. Viable bacteria reduced the non-fluorescent resazurin to the pink, fluorescent resorufin, and thus the fluorescence intensity was directly proportional to the number of metabolically active cells. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of AgNPs that prevented color change, indicating complete inhibition of bacterial viability. The fluorescence signal was measured using a spectrophotometer at excitation/emission wavelengths of 530 or 560 nm (Wypij *et al.*, 2021).

Antioxidant activity of biosynthesized silver nanoparticles

The antioxidant property of biosynthesized AgNPs was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay (Bhakya *et al.*, 2016). Variable concentrations (25, 50, 100, 150, and 200 µg/ml) of synthesized AgNPs preparations were mixed with 0.1 mM methanolic DPPH solution, agitated, and incubated at 37 °C for 30 min in the dark. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 517 nm, corresponding to the reduction of DPPH radicals. Ascorbic acid was used as a positive standard, while a DPPH with distilled water served as the control (Alhage *et al.*, 2018). The percentage of scavenging activity was calculated using the formula: DPPH scavenging activity (%) = $[A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}] / A_{\text{control}} \times 100$.

Anti-inflammatory activity of biosynthesized silver nanoparticles

The anti-inflammatory activity of biosynthesized AgNPs was evaluated *in vitro* using the heat induced protein denaturation assay (Harris *et al.*, 2023). Synthesized AgNPs were prepared in different concentrations (25- 200µg/mL) using phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 6.4) as solvent, while Diclofenac sodium (100µg/ml) served as the standard drug. The assay mixture contained of 0.5 ml of AgNPs solution, 0.5 ml of 0.2% bovine serum albumin (BSA) prepared in PBS and adjusted to pH 6.4. A control was prepared containing BSA and PBS without nanoparticles. All test solutions were incubated at 37°C for 20 min followed by heating at 70°C for 5 min to induce denaturation, then cooled to room temperature. Absorbance was recorded at 660 nm using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of protein denaturation} = [(A1 - A2) / A1] * 100$$

Where, A1 is the absorbance of the control, A2 is the absorbance of the sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative phytochemical analysis

Qualitative phytochemical screening analysis was evaluated on leaf extracts of *Citrus limon* to determine the presence of phytochemicals in the leaves of these medicinal plants. The presence and/or absence of useful bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, phenols, saponins and anthraquinones in leaf extracts were revealed by the confirmatory test, involving color changes and precipitate formation (Figure 3). The results revealed that bioactive compounds like phenols, tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenols and saponins are present and absence of anthraquinones in the leaf extract. For *Citrus limon*, the current results also correspond with those reported by Ali *et al.*, (2017), who identified phenols, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, and alkaloids in ethanolic extracts of *C. limon* leaves, while anthraquinones were absent (Table 1).

Compounds of limonene, β -pinene, neral, sabinene, geranial, geranyl acetate, neryl acetate and geranyl acetate were identified in leaf extracts from *C. limon* (Vekiari *et al.*, 2002). The *C. limon* leaves contain a diverse range of bioactive compounds, particularly secondary metabolites, that contribute to their medicinal value and aromatic profile and there are several biological compounds displaying the strong insecticidal and repellent activity of citrus leaves and their potential role as fumigants (Klimek-Szczykutowicz *et al.*, 2020). The leaves are source of flavonoids such as hesperidin, eriocitrin, diosmin and rutin which exhibit antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Also, phenolic acids like caffeic acid, ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, then alkaloids and tannins contribute to their therapeutic potential (Russo *et al.*, 2015; Paw *et al.*, 2020). Several studies have shown that *C. limon* fruit could be employed to improve human health as antimicrobial and anti-oxidative (Ehiobu *et al.*, 2021), anti-inflammatory (Basli *et al.*, 2016) and anti-tumor products (Dosoky and Setzer, 2018). As it is very rich in bioactive substances, such as citric acid, phenolic compounds flavonoids, and carotenoids and ascorbic acid (Saini *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 3: Phytochemical test from *C. limon* leaf extract. a- Phenols, b- Alkaloids, c- Flavonoids, d-Anthraquinones, e- Terpenoids and steroids, f- Tannins and g- Saponins.

Table 1: Phytochemical screening from *C. limon* leaf extract.

Bioactive phytochemicals	Test	Result
Alkaloids	Mayer's reagent test	+
Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent test	+
Saponins	Frothing test	+
Tannins	a) Ferric chloride test	+
	b) Lead acetate test	+
Terpenoids and Steroids	Salkowski test	+
Phenols	Ferric chloride test	+
Anthraquinones	Bontrager's test	-

+ Present - Absent

Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles

The initial indication of successful synthesis of nanoparticles was visually observed through the gradual color change of the reaction mixture. The reduction of aqueous AgNO_3 solution and *C. limon* leaf extracts led to a transformation from brown to darkish brown, a characteristic change attributed to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) of AgNPs (Figure 4). The phytochemicals present in the plant extracts, including flavonoids, phenolics, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, and terpenoids, represented both as reducing agents for Ag^+ ions and as stabilizing/capping agents, thereby preventing agglomeration and enhancing nanoparticle stability. These findings are in close agreement with earlier reports on *C. limon*, for instance, Shaligram *et al.*, (2009) and Singh *et al.*, (2016) observed a comparable color change when *Citrus* species extracts were employed for silver nanoparticle biosynthesis, further confirming

SPR as a reliable indicator of nanoparticle formation.

Figure 4: Preparation of silver nanoparticles form leaf extracts of *C. limon*. a-Leaf extract, b-silver nitrate and c- silver nanoparticles.

Characterization of silver nanoparticles

UV -Visible spectroscopy analysis

The optical property of the synthesized AgNPs was analyzed using UV-Visible spectroscopy in the wavelength range of 300–600 nm. The *C. limon* -AgNPs exhibited a distinct SPR) peak at 405nm with a maximum absorbance of 0.573 (Figure 5).

The observed SPR bands in the visible region confirm the successful reduction of Ag^+ ions to Ag^0 nanoparticles. In the present study, *C. limon*-AgNPs exhibited SPR peaks at 405 nm, which is reliable with earlier reports of Doan *et al.* (2025) where plant mediated AgNPs displaying absorption maxima in this region. UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis was performed by continuous scanning in the range of 300-900 nm, an effective and widely applied technique for determining the formulation stability of metal nanoparticles with some modification (Niraimathi *et al.*, 2013; Umashankari *et al.*, 2012; Perkampus, 2013; Ray *et al.*, 2015). Maximum absorption peak at 440nm confirms the presence of AgNPs in the synthesized solution. The synthesized AgNPs were dark brown in aqueous solution due to excitation of electrons and changes in electronic energy levels, reflecting the reduction of Ag^+ into Ag^0 (Elemike *et al.*, 2017). Srikar *et al.*, (2016) demonstrated that AgNPs synthesized using green methods typically show absorption peaks in the range of 410–440 nm, with variations attributed to differences in capping agents from biological extracts.

Figure 5: UV -Visible spectroscopy analysis of synthesized AgNPs.

FTIR analysis of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The FTIR spectrum of the synthesized *C. limon*- AgNPs was recorded in the range of 4000–450 cm^{-1} using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum, two spectrophotometer with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 8 scans. The analysis revealed characteristic absorption bands at 2072.96 cm^{-1} , 642.45 cm^{-1} , and 620.55 cm^{-1} (Figure 6). The strong peak at 2072.96 cm^{-1} correspond to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching or possible adsorbed CO- related vibrations, which could originate from bioactive phytoconstituents present in the *C. limon* extract, indicating their involvement in nanoparticle surface capping. The bands at 642.45 cm^{-1} and 620.55 cm^{-1} are located in the low-wavenumber region, typically associated with metal oxygen vibrations, particularly Ag–O stretching modes, confirming the formation of silver–oxygen bonds during nanoparticle synthesis.

The FTIR is an analytical chemical method used to measure the intensity of infrared radiation against its wave number or wavelength light. It was performed to determine the functional groups involved in reducing Ag^+ to AgNPs (Hawar *et al.*, 2022). El-Rafie *et al.*, (2014) who identified medium to strong peaks around 2100 cm^{-1} in citrus mediated AgNPs and ascribed them to stretching vibrations of nitrile and cyanide groups derived from phytoconstituents. Similarly, Jyoti *et al.* (2022) noted that the presence of CO and CN functional groups in *Spondias pinnata* extracts played a role in nanoparticle capping and stabilization. Comparable results were obtained by Mustapha *et al.* (2023), who reported AgO stretching bands in *Citrus aurantifolia* mediated AgNPs. Khane *et al.* (2022) demonstrated that aqueous leaf extract mediated AgNPs exhibited a distinct (SPR) band at 475 nm, with FTIR analysis confirming

the involvement of flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and citric acid in nanoparticle reduction and stabilization. Sathyavathi *et al.* (2010) demonstrated that AgNPs synthesized using *Coriandrum sativum* extract exhibited distinct FTIR absorption bands for C–O and N–H stretching, confirming the presence of proteins and enzymes involved in the reduction process. Furthermore, Mittal *et al.*, (2013) emphasized that FTIR spectroscopy can track surface modifications of AgNPs when coated with polymers or biomolecules, which is crucial for biomedical applications.

Figure 6: FTIR Analysis of *C. limon* AgNPs.

Scanning electron microscopy analysis of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The SEM micrograph reveals the surface morphology and size distribution of AgNPs synthesized using lemon extract as a biogenic reducing and stabilizing agent. The nanoparticles predominantly exhibit irregular to nearly flake like morphologies, with noticeable aggregation. Particle size measurements from selected regions range from 79.4 nm to 222 nm, with individual sizes recorded as 79.4 nm, 99.2 nm, 198 nm, and 222 nm, giving an average particle size of approximately 149.65 nm, indicating a relatively broad and polydisperse distribution. The observed agglomeration is likely due to bioactive compounds in lemon extract, such as citric acid, ascorbic acid, and polyphenols, which reduce silver ions and form an organic coating around nanoparticles (Figure 7).

Scanning electron microscopy is a widely used method in materials research, particularly for studying surface topography, morphology and composition. In this technique, a focused beam

of high –energy electrons are directed onto the sample’s surface (Azimzadeh *et al.*, 2025). By detecting and interpreting these signals, it is possible to produce high-resolution images and obtain detailed information about the surface features and structure of the sample. Such images are presented extensively in the referenced photographs (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). By capturing and analyzing these signals, SEM produces highly detailed images that reveal the specimen’s surface topography, morphology and composition (Ali *et al.*, 2023). According to Goldstein *et al.*, (2017), SEM operates by scanning a focused electron beam across the sample, producing signals that are detected and transformed into detailed surface images. This makes SEM an essential tool for confirming nanoparticle formation and evaluating synthesis efficiency. Similar results have been reported by Aygün *et al.* (2020), who synthesized AgNPs using *Citrus limon* extract and observed particle sizes ranging from 50 to 120 nm with some degree of agglomeration. In another study, Ahmed *et al.*, (2016) reported irregularly shaped AgNPs within the size range of 80–150 nm when using citrus-based phytochemicals, highlighting the influence of organic acids and polyphenols on morphology. SEM not only allows for the visualization of nanoparticle size and shape but also reveals the degree of agglomeration and surface smoothness, which are critical for understanding nanoparticle stability.

Figure 7 Scanning electron microscopy analysis of *C. limon*– silver nanoparticles.

X ray diffraction analysis of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The XRD pattern of *C. limon*– AgNPs displayed five prominent peaks at 2θ values of 38° , 44.04° , 45.63° , 64.29° , and 77.28° , corresponding to the (111), (200), (210), (220), and (311) crystallographic planes of face-centered cubic silver. The sharp and intense diffraction peak at 38° indexed to the (111) plane indicates that the (111) orientation is predominant, which is a common feature in green-synthesized AgNPs. These reflections are consistent with the

standard JCPDS card No. 04-0783, confirming the formation of pure crystalline AgNPs. The average crystallite size, as estimated from the Debye–Scherrer equation, was found to be in the nanometer range, validating the successful synthesis of nanosized AgNPs. The broader nature of the peaks further indicates reduced crystallite size and slight lattice strain due to capping by phytochemicals present in lemon extract (Figure 8).

Comparable findings have been reported by Khane *et al.*, (2022), who characterized AgNPs synthesized using *Citrus limon* zest extract and identified XRD peaks at $2\theta \approx 38.18^\circ$, 44.34° , 64.53° , and 77.46° , corresponding to the (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes of a face-centered cubic silver lattice-closely matching the present observation. The AgNPs prepared from *Morinda lucida* leaf extract typically exhibit face-centered cubic crystallinity with XRD peaks at $2\theta \approx 38^\circ$, 44° , 64° , and 77° corresponding to the (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes (Labulo *et al.*, 2022). According to Ahmed *et al.*, (2016), the absence of extraneous peaks in XRD spectra indicates the purity of AgNPs, while the presence of additional peaks may signify organic or inorganic capping agents from plant extracts.

Figure 8: X ray diffraction analysis of *C. limon*– silver nanoparticles.

Antibacterial activity of synthesized silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The antibacterial activity of synthesized *C. limon* AgNPs against pathogenic microbes was shown in Figure 9. Zone of inhibition increases with concentrations 25, 50, 75, 100, 150, 200 μ g/ml. The highest zone of inhibition 16 mm for *B. subtilis* and 15 mm for *E. mori* was observed at 200 μ g/ml. While the lowest zone of inhibition 8 mm for *B. subtilis* and 7 mm for *E. mori* was observed at 25 μ g/ml (Figure 9). The positive control chloramphenicol was showed zone of inhibition of 24.6mm. These findings are consistent with previous reports on

AgNPs, where Alzubaidi *et al.*, (2023) observed inhibition zones of against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and Niluxsshun *et al.*, (2021) reported zones of 18–21 mm for *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* using leaf and zest extracts.

Plant-mediated AgNPs from *C. limon* leaves owe their broad antimicrobial spectrum to multiple pathways including cell membrane disruption and induction of oxidative stress. Latest studies on green synthesized AgNPs reported consistent antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant properties across diverse plant systems, with citrus leaves frequently cited as effective bioresources (Kifle *et al.*, 2025; Eker *et al.*, 2025). Guzzatti *et al.*, (2025) highlighted the potential of biosynthesized AgNPs in wound healing applications, where their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties accelerate tissue regeneration and reduce infection risk. Dhanavade *et al.*, (2011) reported that *Citrus lemon* L. was effective against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and compounds like coumarin and tetrazene were present in the lemon peel extract. These zest-mediated AgNPs also showed strong DPPH radical scavenging activity and antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans*, reinforcing the role of citrus phytochemicals in nanoparticle reduction, capping, and biological efficacy (Khane *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 9: Antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts. a – *B. subtilis*. b – *E. coli*.

Minimum inhibitory concentration analysis of silver nanoparticles

The MIC assay of *C. limon* AgNPs demonstrated a dose dependent antimicrobial effect, as evident from the progressive increase in percentage inhibition with rising concentrations. At the lowest tested concentration of 5 µg/ml, the inhibition was minimal 9.09%, while a noticeable increase was observed at higher concentrations, reaching 63.64% inhibition at 160

$\mu\text{g/ml}$. This indicates that the nanoparticles effectively suppressed microbial growth in a concentration dependent manner, which is consistent with the well-established antimicrobial potential of biogenically synthesized AgNPs (Table 2 and Figure 10). As Ildiz *et al.*, (2021) reported biosynthesized AgNPs demonstrated low MIC values against multidrug-resistant strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, confirming their strong antimicrobial potential. Similarly, Gurunathan *et al.*, (2014) determined MICs of green-synthesized AgNPs against clinical pathogens, showing dose-dependent inhibition consistent with results from agar diffusion assays.

Table 2: Minimum inhibitory concentration of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts.

Sample	Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	O.D @ 540nm	% of inhibition
<i>C. limon</i> AgNPs	Control	0.77	0.00
	5	0.70	9.09
	10	0.63	18.18
	20	0.52	32.47
	40	0.40	48.05
	80	0.33	57.14
	160	0.28	63.64

Figure 10: Minimum inhibitory concentration of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts.

Antioxidant activity of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The antioxidant activity of ascorbic acid (standard) was assessed using the DPPH radical scavenging assay and the results revealed a strong dose-dependent increase in free radical inhibition (Figure 11). At lower concentrations (25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), ascorbic acid exhibited 24.78% inhibition, which progressively increased to 67.76% at 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

The nanoparticles demonstrated a concentration-dependent increase in radical scavenging activity, with inhibition ranging from 9.2% at 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 32.3% at 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Although the activity was comparatively lower than the standard ascorbic acid, the steady increase suggests that the phytochemicals present in *C. limon* extract, which act as reducing and capping agents during nanoparticle synthesis, play a key role in imparting antioxidant potential. Anandalakshmi *et al.*, (2016) documented that citrus leaf-mediated AgNPs demonstrated only moderate DPPH radical scavenging, always lower than vitamin C but superior to crude extracts due to the stabilizing effect of phytochemicals on nanoparticles which corroborated with our results.

Figure 11: DPPH assay of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts.

Anti-inflammatory activity of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts

The anti-inflammatory activity of *C. limon* derived AgNPs increased in a concentration dependent manner (Figure 12) with inhibition values ranging from 8.45% at 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 20.41% at 200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Thus, the BSA denaturation method continues to serve as an effective tool for assessing the anti-inflammatory potential of bioactive substances, bridging preclinical screening and therapeutic applications. According to Chou (2018), the consistency of the BSA denaturation assay lies in its simplicity, reproducibility, and correlation with *in vivo* anti-inflammatory activity, making it a standard protocol for preliminary screening of drugs, plant extracts, and nanomaterials. In contrast, a study by Niluxsshun *et al.*, (2021) reported that AgNPs synthesized using *C. limon* extract exhibited higher anti-inflammatory activity, indicating a more potent effect compared to the leaf-derived AgNPs in this study. Additionally, research by Eker *et al.*, (2025) on AgNPs demonstrated significant anti-

inflammatory effects, suggesting that different parts of the plant may yield AgNPs with varying degrees of anti-inflammatory potency.

Figure 12: Anti-inflammatory assay of silver nanoparticles from *C. limon* leaf extracts.

CONCLUSION

Overall, this study not only confirms the biomedical relevance of *Citrus limon* leaf mediated AgNPs but also highlights the strategic advantage of employing combined phytochemical sources for enhanced bioactivity. Compared with conventional chemical AgNPs synthesis, which often poses toxicity risks and environmental concerns, the present green synthesis approach is cost-effective, biocompatible, and scalable. Hence, the conclusion emphasizes that *C. limon* AgNPs represent a promising candidate for future applications in antimicrobial therapeutics, antioxidant nutraceuticals and anti-inflammatory formulations. Moving forward, mechanistic studies, nanotoxicological profiling, and *in vivo* validations are essential to bridge the gap between laboratory synthesis and clinical or pharmaceutical translation.

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